

PERIPHRASES AS A STYLISTIC DEVICE IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The language has rich resources to make the language more colourful and interesting to be heard. Stylistic devices play an important role to deal with the quality of the language. To be more specific, periphrases is considered to be the important stylistics device in linguistics

Key words: Periphrases, linguistics, stylistic device, language, culture

INTRODUCTION

It is generally agreed that language and culture are closely related. Language can be seen as verbal expression of culture. Different languages will create different limitations therefore people who share a culture but speak different languages, will have different world views. Obviously, this happens with periphrasing the names of celebrities in different languages and cultures. The values, merits in languages are revealed also with these periphrasis units of famous personas. Still language is rooted in culture and culture is reflected and passed on by languages from generation to generation. Therefore, we decided to research linguocultural and semantic features of the periphrasis units of the names of famous people in English and Uzbek languages. Their matching and characteristic peculiarities will be investigated.

Foreign and local linguistic scholars have conducted great deal of research on studying the notion of periphrases. Indisputably, the notion of periphrasis is defined in various characterizations, for instance in the Webster's dictionary as following "...denotes the use of a longer phrasing in place of a possible shorter and plainer form of expression. Originally, the word periphrasis comes from the Greek word *periphrazein*, which is made up of the prefix "*peri-*" meaning "round about" and "*phrazein*" meaning "to declare." Paraphrase, recitation texts with own words.¹⁸

METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the goal of this article, over 10 articles which are related to the topic have been investigated. The researcher adopts descriptive and empirical analytical approaches as far as data collection and discussion are concerned. Moreover,

¹⁸ Словарь русского языка 1999; (электронная версия).

in order to compare academic writing and text language, the comparative method is utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Linguist scholar Galperin defines the term of periphrasis, viz “Viewed from the angle of its linguistic nature, periphrasis represents the renaming of an object and as such may be considered along with a more general group of word designations replacing the direct names of their denotata”. Instead of directly stating some certain words or expressions, sometimes the writer or speaker implements its meaning with alternative or synonymic ones. To illustrate, *an announcement about incredible show of the “forest king” (lion)*. Galperin states, “Traditionally, language or dictionary periphrases and the words they stand for are synonyms by nature, the periphrasis being expressed by a word-combination. Periphrasis as a stylistic device is a new, genuine nomination of an object, a process which realizes the power of language to coin new names for objects by disclosing some quality of the object, even though it may be transitory, and making it alone represent the object”. As an example, in the *Great Gatsby*, Daisy is referred to as - ‘the girl who leaves the top down in a borrowed convertible’.¹⁹

L. V. Grehneva explains the meaning of the notion of periphrasis in this way periphrasis is a descriptive expression of nominative character. Combination of periphrasis, expressing the object, renders to name its characteristically signs.²⁰

Periphrasis- it is a phenomenon, does not have unambiguous understanding in linguistics science. It can be defined as descriptive expression, and as trope, often identify with other language units- with phraseologies and phrases.²¹

According to professor Ashurova “periphrasis is the use of a longer and roundabout phrase instead of a possible shorter one with the aim of indicating a new feature of a phenomenon”.²² The scholar K. Musayev advocates the concept in this way “the concept of such renaming of an object with a phrase is easily understood by the reader within the context”. The scholar claims that with periphrases some certain words, expression and set phrases can be replaced by other words that are understood to the reader or listener. Additionally, according to Musayev, words of periphrases examples are understood even without context, as they are synonymic versions of the words.²³

¹⁹ I. R. Galperin. “Stylistics”. 1981 p.169

²⁰ N. A. Zabolotsky’s Poetry”. L. V. Grehneva “Objects of Periphrasis in. 2010 p.504

²¹ L. V. Grehneva “On some aspects of periphrastic nomination”.. 2009 p.207

²² Ashurova D.U., Galiyeva M.R. Stylistics of literary text. Turon-Iqbol, Tashkent, 2016, p.235.

²³ Q. Musayev. English stylistics. 2003 p.119

When a writer or speaker uses a multitude of words to express a thought-instead of coming out and stating it directly and succinctly-it is called periphrasis.

Periphrasis might be used for many different reasons. Among these are that the writer or speaker wants the reader to be confused, or the person stating the thought is attempting to appear more intelligent by talking around the point and using "big words." Instead of saying, "I lost my homework," you say, "As a matter of fact, the assignment in question is temporarily unavailable due to the secrecy of its location."

Instead of saying, "I got a C on the paper," you tell your parents, "There was room for improvement in the organization and support of my ideas, and while Mrs. Smith recognized my attempts to be brief and forthright, she would appreciate additional substance in my argument."²⁴

“Periphrasis is both a grammatical principle and manner of speaking that uses more words than necessary to evoke a certain meaning. Periphrasis is, at times, beneficial for certain reasons, though is often considered redundant. Some examples of periphrasis are purposeful in order to evade a taboo subject, such as in the case of innuendo and euphemism, or to adorn a sentence in a poetic way. People with aphasia, a language disorder usually caused by brain damage, are sometimes afflicted with a difficulty of coming up with the right words and might employ periphrasis as a technique to get to a certain meaning. This is true as well of many people learning a new language. For example, a person might not know or remember the word for “bee” in a different language and instead say, “a yellow and black thing that makes honey”.²⁵

This device has a long history. It was widely used in the Bible and in Homer’s Iliad. As a poetic device, it was very popular in Latin poetry (Virgil). Due to this influence, it became an important feature of epic and descriptive poetry throughout the middle Ages and into the Renaissance. It is due to this practice of re-naming things that periphrasis became one of the most favored devices in the 17th and 18th centuries giving birth even to a special trend in literature in France and other countries called periphrastic. There exists in English a whole battery of phrases, which are still used as periphrastic synonyms (see below) for ordinary denominations of things and phenomena.

V. N. Yartseva quotes S. K. Workman, an English literature scholar who states "the most pervasive element in the aureate style—and the most vitiating—was periphrasis." Prof. Yartseva states that the use of periphrasis in the 16th century was in the nature of embellishment, thus justifying the attribute aureate, and that periphrasis became a feature of a definite literary style.

²⁴ http://www.softschools.com/examples/literary_terms/periphrasis_examples

²⁵ <http://www.literarydevices.com/periphrasis/>

CONCLUSION

The notion of periphrasis has been analyzed and defined in various ways by many linguistic scholar. Summarizing the definitions above, we affirm that periphrasis is accepted as a stylistic device to swap the definite words with their related meaning substitutes that are grasped straightforwardly. Sentence structure can be changed or the words may be replaced with their synonymic versions keeping the meaning of the previous one. The periphrasis words or expressions can be understood both within and without context. The speech, narrations, texts can be more colorful and diverse, avoiding repetitions.

REFERENCES:

1. Ashurova D.U., Galiyeva M.R. Stylistics of literary text. Turon-Iqbol, Tashkent, 2016, p.235.
2. I. R. Galperin. "Stylistics". 1981 p.169
3. L. V. Grehneva "On some aspects of periphrastic nomination".. 2009 p.207
4. N. A. Zabolotsky's Poetry". L. V. Grehneva "Objects of Periphrasis in. 2010 p.504
5. Q. Musayev. English stylistics. 2003 p.119
6. http://www.softschools.com/examples/literary_terms/periphrasis_examples
7. <http://www.literarydevices.com/periphrasis/>